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WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY | D2.10 Data on regulatory and socioeconomic conditions and impacts | V3.0 | P

HORIZON EUROPE PROGRAMME – TOPIC HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05

Wind energy in the natural and social environment

Research and Innovation action (RIA)

wimby
WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

Wind in My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU

Grant Agreement No. 101083460

Starting date: 1st January 2023 – Duration: 36 months

Deliverable D2.10

Data on regulatory and socioeconomic conditions and impacts (b)

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable number	D2.10
Deliverable title	Data on regulatory and socioeconomic conditions and impacts (b)
Work Package	WP2
Deliverable type¹	R
Dissemination level²	P
Due date	31.12.2024 (Month 24)
Pages	71
Document version³	3.0
Lead author(s)	Monika Bucha (KIE), Andrei del Villar (UU), Luis Ramirez Camargo (UU)
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The WIMBY project has received funding from the European Union's research and innovation programme Horizon Europe under the grant agreement No. 101083460. This document reflects only the author's view, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

¹ Type: ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot; R: Report; D: Demonstrator

² Dissemination level: C: Confidential; P: Public

³ First digit: 0: draft; 1: peer review; 2: peer review 3: coordinator approval; 4: final version

DOCUMENT CHANGE HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description
DRAFT			
0.1	04.11.2024	Monika Bucha (KIE), Andrei del Villar (UU), Luis Ramirez Camargo (UU)	Creation
FIRST PEER REVIEW			
1.0	11.12.2024	Shary Heuinckx (VUB), Mariana Carvalho (APREN)	Proofreading and peer review
1.1	16.12.2024	Monika Bucha (KIE)	Consolidation of input from reviewers
1.2	23.12.2024	Luis Ramirez Camargo (UU)	Consolidation of input from reviewers
COORDINATOR APPROVAL			
2.0	24.12.2024	Shary Heuinckx (VUB)	Coordinator review
2.1	24.12.2024	Luis Ramirez Camargo (UU)	Consolidation of input from coordinator
2.2	24.12.2024	Shary Heuinckx (VUB)	Coordinator approval
FINAL VERSION			
3.0	24.12.2024	Shary Heuinckx (VUB)	Format review, version ready for submission

SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract

This deliverable presents, in a first part, an overview of the finalised datasets on regulations affecting the deployment of and public acceptance of wind energy in Europe. Key areas covered include wind energy zones, setback distances from residential areas and other types of infrastructure, noise limits, shadow flicker, and financial compensation schemes. Moreover, concerning job creation, the model defined in D2.9 has been ported to python and we have developed a python package that can be used stand alone or integrated in the WIMBY interactive map. The model can estimate direct, indirect and induced job creation for each stage in the lifetime (development, construction, manufacturing, operation and maintenance and decommissioning) of individual wind farms based on data that is publicly available in scientific and grey literature.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
bn	billion
dB	decibel
DKK	Danish krone
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EUR	Euro
GBP	British pound sterling
GW	gigawatts
kW	kilowatts
m	metres
max	maximum
min	minimum
MSP	Maritima Spatial Planning
MW	Megawatts
MWh	Megawatts per hour
MVA	Megavolt-amperes
sec.	seconds
UK	United Kingdom
VOR	very high frequency omnidirectional range station

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is the finalisation of the work that has been presented in deliverable D2.9 (Data on regulatory and socioeconomic conditions and impacts (b)) in December 2023. It contains an extended analysis of rules and regulations governing wind energy development, focussing on ten, “WIMBY countries”, namely, on Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Austria, Portugal, Switzerland, Norway, and the United Kingdom.

This deliverable is closely connected to WP3 which creates an interactive WIMBY-Map online. The regulatory data, particularly the data on setback distances to residential areas and other types of infrastructure will be included in the map to inform stakeholders about the policies governing wind energy development in their area of interests.

The objective of this deliverable is to create regulatory datasets on rules and regulations governing wind power development and governance models that affect the acceptance towards wind power installations. The collection of the data is based on an in-depth literature review and semi-structured interviews with wind energy experts across the continent.

Key research questions and take aways include:

- **What measures have the EU, and its Member States, implemented to fast-track wind energy development, and how might these affect public acceptance? (Section 3.1)**

Measures taken include the requirement for Member States to presume renewable energy projects serve the overriding public interest and the requirement for Member States to designate Renewables Acceleration Areas for renewables to ensure faster permitting. Given the seemingly stringent enforcement of these measures, the EU, however, at the same time requires Member States to promote public acceptance through direct and indirect participation of communities.

- **How advanced are Member States with the definition of Renewable Acceleration Areas or designated wind energy zones which are supported to speed of wind energy development? (Section 3.2)**

Onshore wind energy zoning varies widely across European countries, with approaches ranging from strict legislative frameworks to voluntary regional planning strategies. Table 2 contains a comprehensive

overview comparing the introduction and definition of wind energy zones in the selected countries.

- **What considerations inform the design of setback distances to residential areas and other types of infrastructure? Are these distances consistent across Europe, or do notable differences exist? (Section 3.3.)**

Summarising **Annex A**, it can be noted that setback distances to residential areas vary significantly across Europe. For example, the minimum distance in the federal state of Bremen, Germany, and the Flemish region in Belgium is as low as 250 m metres, whereas in Bavaria, Germany, it can extend to as much as ten times the turbine's tip. Unlike setback distances for other types of infrastructure, those to residential areas are often shaped more by political considerations and efforts to appease local communities than by rigorous risk assessment.

- **What other regulations have been introduced to mitigate the negative externalities of wind turbines, and have these measures been harmonised across Europe? (Section 3.3)**

Setback distances to key infrastructure such as motorways, transmission lines, and railway lines, are a critical component of wind energy planning. Our research highlights that here, typically formulas are used to calculate the setback distance (for instance, 1.2 times the tip height in Austria). Interviewees highlighted that strict setback distances can pose challenges to wind energy development, reinforcing the need for flexible, case-by-case assessments.

In addition, a case-by-case analysis is typically required as well, considering factors such as elevation (longer shadows in elevated areas), location (higher probability of ice-throw in colder regions), wind direction, and proximity to existing infrastructure can significantly affect the calculation and the resulting setback distance.

- **What financial participation schemes exist in selected European countries to compensate municipalities and citizens living near wind parks? (Section 3.4)**

Financial participation schemes for wind energy projects vary across Europe in several aspects: the type of participation (e.g., wind energy shares or pre-set payments), the calculation formula for compensation (e.g., per wind turbine or per MW/year), the group of beneficiaries (e.g., municipalities or citizens), and the compensation amount itself.

Also, while certain Member States have legally enshrined such schemes, obligating wind park developers to compensate affected municipalities and citizens, others have not. Thereby, financial participation and compensation schemes do have a significant impact on local acceptance (Knauf, 2022; Vuichard et al., 2019).

Despite the positive signal these schemes offer, there is still room for improvement. For instance, only few of these schemes oblige wind park operators to offer municipalities or citizens to become a shareholder in the project. Thereby, such an approach would not only be in line with the Dutch target to achieve 50% shared ownership in large energy projects by 2030, but in general, include citizens in the energy transition and share profits in a more equitable way. That such an approach is called for, has become especially evident during the gas price explosion of 2022–23, which led the EU to introduce a law requiring energy companies to share excess profits with the general public. Also – irrespective of whether a municipality acquires “wind energy money” through project shares or by receiving a fixed amount of payments – the question of what happens next is rarely addressed in the regulations or the guidelines. Who decides how the wind energy money is being spent? One pioneering effort is a guideline presented by Denmark; here, it lays out in great detail how municipalities should organise the distribution of wind energy money. In addition, the guideline lays out that municipalities themselves are excluded from applying for the fund, making sure that it is the interests of the citizens and local companies who are met.

Moreover, in this deliverable we present the python version of the job creation model defined in D2.9. This can be used stand alone or integrated in the WIMBY interactive map. The model can estimate direct, indirect and induced job creation for each stage in the lifetime (development, construction, manufacturing, operation and maintenance and decommissioning) of individual wind farms based on data that is publicly available in scientific and grey literature. For details on the data acquisition, we refer to D2.9. In D2.10 we provide two alternative models coming from the same data. The first one relies on descriptive statistics and is updatable (in case the user has additional data) but cannot take into consideration the turbine size. The second one, described in D2.9, relies on regression models for the variables for which sufficient data was available. This one cannot be directly updated but can

make use of the full set of inputs: turbine capacity, number of turbines, country of deployment, and whether the installation is onshore or offshore. The package only requires the python packages pandas and numpy to run. The underlying data set has been included in github with the expectation that new data will be added from other new projects by other researchers.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Wind energy targets at the European level

The revised Renewable Energy Directive (European Commission, 2023a), raises the European Union's (EU) renewable energy target, requiring Member States to ensure renewables comprise at least 42,5% of the EU's gross final energy consumption. A scenario presented by the European Commission (2021) estimates this will necessitate 30 GW of new wind installations annually, equating to approximately 10,000 wind turbines, depending on size and location. These figures may need further adjustment to account for the AI revolution, which, according to McKinsey (2024), could more than triple European energy demand by 2030.

In 2023, the EU installed a record 16.2 GW of new wind capacity, 79% of which was onshore (WindEurope, 2024a). However, this represents only half the capacity needed annually to meet the EU's renewable energy targets. To accelerate wind energy development, the European Commission, the Member States, and industry stakeholders collaborated on drafting plans and charters with symbolic significance, aiming to strengthen investor confidence in the sector.

In October 2023, the EC presented 6 pillars and 15 actions to strengthen the European wind power industry in its **European Wind Power Action Plan** (2023b), with "faster permitting and increased predictability" identified as a central pillar. Two months later, the vast majority of EU Member States, alongside leading industry representatives, reaffirmed their commitment to expanding wind energy production both onshore and offshore by signing the **European Wind Charter** (European Commission, 2023c).

At the same event, 21 EU countries submitted non-legally binding **pledges on wind energy deployment volumes** (European Union, 2023). Among the WIMBY partner countries, the following additional onshore wind energy capacities (in MW) were pledged for the period 01/2024–12/2026: Germany

(23,600), Belgium (937.5), Italy (5,100), Austria (1,200), Denmark (508) and the Netherlands (400). For offshore wind energy during the same period, the Netherlands pledged 1,500 MW and Denmark 1,489 MW. For the shorter period 01/2024–12/2025, Portugal pledged to add 1,665 MW onshore and 395 MW offshore.

1.2 Challenges faced by the European wind energy sector

Wind energy, both onshore (92% of installed wind energy capacity) and offshore, is a cornerstone of the European electricity system (European Commission, 2023c). In 2022, it supplied on average of 15% of the electricity consumed in the EU (Eurostat, 2023). Across much of Europe, wind energy remains the **cheapest source** of electricity (Georgakaki et al., 2022). Despite this, the sector faces critical challenges, including intensifying international competition, limited access to raw materials, and financial barriers.

Another challenge faced by the wind energy industry is **insufficient grid capacity** and the associated **curtailment costs**. Without swift action, redispatch volumes could increase nearly six-fold by 2040 (Joint Research Centre, 2024). As of 2024, over 500 GW of potential wind energy capacity across European countries is awaiting grid connection assessments (WindEurope, 2024b). Grid curtailment costs exceeded EUR 2 bn in Spain in 2023 (Hewitt, 2024) and EUR 4 bn in Germany in 2022 (Bundesnetzagentur, 2023). In Germany, grid curtailment costs are socialised through grid fees, which are paid by consumers (Joos and Staffell, 2018).

In addition to geopolitical and technological challenges, **low levels of acceptance** among local stakeholders often lead to lengthy permitting procedures. A study by a German wind energy association (Quentin, 2019), which analysed 405 wind farms with a combined capacity of 1,332 MW, found that approximately 20% of these turbines faced legal challenges. The primary plaintiffs are nature protection organisations (61%), private individuals (36%), citizen groups (14%) and municipalities (12%). The most common reasons for lawsuits were concerns about bird and bats (48%), nature (24%), noise (17%), zoning issues (10%), health concerns (6%), and monument conservation (6%).

To address public concerns, some countries introduced **strict wind energy regulations**. An extreme example is Hungary, which initially set setback distances to residential areas at 12 kilometres, though this was reduced to 700

metres in December 2023 (Bird&Bird, 2024). Another prominent example is Bavaria’s 10H regulation, requiring a minimum setback distance of ten times the total turbine height. While the regulation was partially relaxed in 2022, it still applies in specific cases (Bayrische Staatsregierung, 2022).

1.3 Porting the Job Creation model to python

For this deliverable we have ported the excel-based job creation model defined in D2.9 to python and have created a package that can be used stand alone or integrated in the WIMBY interactive map. Additionally, we have created an alternative simplified model that works based on the descriptive statistics of the collected data set on job creation. The advantage of this last one is that it can directly take into consideration new available data included by the user in the job creation data set. The disadvantage is that the model only takes into consideration the number of turbines, country of deployment, and whether the installation is onshore or offshore, leaving aside the turbine capacity. The original model described in D2.9 relies on regression models for the variables for which sufficient data was available. This one cannot be directly updated but can make use of the full set of inputs: turbine capacity, number of turbines, country of deployment, and whether the installation is onshore or offshore.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Semi-structured interviews with wind energy experts

Between July and November 2024, we conducted seventeen semi-structured interviews with twenty wind energy experts from the WIMBY partner countries and two organisations working on a European level (see Table 1). Participants, each with a minimum of five years wind energy experience, were selected to provide insights into wind energy governance, setback distances, and other restrictions. The interviews were conducted online via Microsoft Teams and, if consent was given, recorded for internal purposes .

Table 1: Expert Interviews (July – November 2024)

COUNTRIES	SECTORS	EXPERIENCE
Belgium	WE developer	5 years
Belgium	WE developer	5 years
Denmark	WE consultant	18 years
Germany	Government	7 years
Italy	Marine research institute	19 years
Italy	WE developer	5 years
Netherlands	WE consultant	20 years

Austria	WE association	25 years
Austria	WE developer	7 years
Portugal	WE association	6 years
Portugal	WE association	9 years
Switzerland	Government	20 years
Switzerland	Government	13 years
Norway	Government	21 years
Norway	WE consultant	15 years
United Kingdom	WE consultant	14 years
United Kingdom	WE consultant	24 years
EU27	WE association	5 years
EU27	Marine research Institute	5 years
EU27	Marine research Institute	7 years

The interviews were based on a pre-designed questionnaire and covered the following topics: wind energy zones (Section 3.2), setback distances to residential areas (section 3.3.1), setback distances to other types of infrastructure onshore (Section 3.3.2.), setback distances to other types of infrastructure offshore (Section 3.3.3), noise limits (Section 3.3.4), shadow flicker (Section 3.3.5) and financial participation schemes (Section 3.4).

Prior to the interviews, we conducted an extensive web search to gather preliminary information on key themes, including existing policies and regulations. During the interviews, participants were asked to confirm the accuracy of this data or provide additional sources or insights. In cases where gaps or discrepancies were identified, the interviewees shared relevant links or documentation, which were subsequently used to supplement and validate the data.

This approach aligns with the methodology described by Magaldi and Berler (2020) who emphasise that semi-structured interviews are flexible and versatile, making them a popular choice for collecting qualitative data. This method facilitated a comprehensive understanding of the regulatory frameworks and practical challenges associated with wind energy development across the specified countries.

2.2 Porting the job creation model

For the porting process we have decided to review our data set of job creation data created and provided in D2.9. for consistency. This to ensure that excluded and included references met appropriate criteria, as well as

identify outliers in the dataset. Specifically, the source Vasconcellos & Caido Couto (2021) was identified as an outlier (the provided values are several times higher than the average of other sources), and was therefore excluded from the dataset used for the model. Additionally, the model was updated to expand the list of manufacturing countries to include additional locations based on data reported in the windfarms location data set of thewindpower.net. This included the addition of Poland, Portugal, Italy, and the United Kingdom to the pre-established manufacturing countries which were Germany, Spain, and Denmark.

While conducting the consistency check of the data we decided to create a second alternative of the job creation model that merely relies on descriptive statistics. This one cannot take into consideration the size of individual turbines as parameter but can be updated by adding new data to the job creation data set.

The two models, the one described in D2.9 and the new simplified one, were implemented as individual functions in a python package relying on the python packages pandas and numpy.

3. REGULATIONS GOVERNING WIND ENERGY DEVELOPMENT

3.1 European measures to support the wind energy industry

After the Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, the EU introduced several measures to accelerate wind energy development (European Commission, 2022), which were later defined in greater detail in the revised Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2023/2413, commonly referred to as RED III.

The following paragraphs focus on three key measures: (1) the requirement for Member States to presume renewable energy projects serve the overriding public interest; (2) the requirement for Member States to designate “go-to areas” (Renewables Acceleration Areas) for renewables to ensure faster permitting; and (3) the requirement for Member States to promote public acceptance through direct and indirect participation of local communities (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Selected measures taken in Directive (EU) 2023/2413

According to Article 16f of RED III “Member States shall ensure that, in the permit-granting procedure, the planning, construction and operation of renewable energy plants, the connection of such plants to the grid, the related grid itself, and storage assets are presumed as being in the **overriding public interest** and serving public health and safety when balancing legal interests in individual cases” with other legal interests.

These “other” legal interests are enshrined in the Council Directive of 21 May 1991 on the **conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora**, Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community Action in the field of **water policy**, and Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 30 November 2009 on the **conservation of wild birds**.

According to Article 15c and 16a of RED III, “[b]y **21 February 2026**, Member States shall ensure that competent authorities adopt one or more plans designating [...] **renewables acceleration areas** for one or more types of renewable energy sources. [...]” These should be areas particularly suitable for such projects, based on the expectation that the deployed renewable energy source will have minimal environmental impact.

Member States must ensure that the permit-granting procedures for renewable energy projects do not exceed **12 months** for onshore projects and **24 months** for offshore projects within renewables acceleration areas. Outside these areas, the maximum permitting duration is set at 24 months for onshore and 26 months for offshore projects. As of 2022, no Member State had an average permitting duration below 24 months, with Romania being the fastest country at 30 months and Croatia the slowest 120 months (Fox et al., 2022).

Given the existing challenges in identifying suitable areas for wind energy development without sparking local conflicts (Langer et al., 2016), an overly stringent enforcement of this “push” could exacerbate tensions between

wind park developers and residents. Recognising this risk, Article 15d of RED III urges Member States to “*promote public acceptance of renewable energy projects by means of direct and indirect participation of local communities*”. The European Commission highlights measures such as reduced electricity costs and financial participation schemes as practical approaches to increase public acceptance (European Commission, 2024).

3.2 Wind energy zones

3.2.1 General information

In the wind energy sector, **suitability zones** refer to areas deemed as particularly appropriate for wind energy projects, based on factors such as high wind potential, proximity to grid infrastructure, and minimal conflict with environmental or societal interests. The European Commission (2024) has issued guidance for Member States on the designation of Renewables Acceleration Areas, emphasising the importance of considering grid capacity when identifying these zones.

In contrast, **exclusion zones** are areas where wind energy installations are prohibited due to legal, environmental, or safety constraints. Examples include nature conservation parks, military zones, densely populated areas, or regions with aviation restrictions. The delineation of these zones serves to balance energy production goals with ecological preservation and community acceptance, thereby mitigating legal conflicts and expediting permitting processes – both crucial for meeting renewable energy targets.

The European Commission has also made available digitally consolidated datasets on various energy and environmental factors through the **Energy and Industry Geography Lab**. This geospatial data hub assists Member States in identifying go-to areas for the rapid deployment of wind and solar installations. Since May 2022, the Lab provides an interactive visual representation of consolidated information on a wide range of relevant factors (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Energy and Industry Geography Lab (last update: 1 February 2024)

Datasets used to identify Renewables Acceleration Areas for onshore wind energy include Natura 2000 sites, nationally designated protected areas, key biodiversity areas, and important bird areas. For offshore wind energy, the Energy and Industry Geography Lab provides data on ecologically or biologically significant marine areas, underwater noise, human pressure on marine species, peatlands and other relevant factors.

The European Commission offers additional information on offshore wind energy through its **European Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) Platform**. MSP is an integrative process to address the growing demand for maritime space from both traditional and emerging sectors (such as the wind energy sector), while ensuring the preservation and proper functioning of marine ecosystems (European MSP Platform and European Commission, 2020).

As part of the EU's **Integrated Maritime Policy** (European Commission, 2007), the European MSP Platform signifies a shift from traditional single-sector planning to a more integrated approach to maritime spatial planning. Each Member State with access to the sea is expected to publish an MSP. Figure 3 highlights the countries that had completed this task as of September 2020. The European MSP Platform also provides access to national MSP, typically accompanied by a shortened, translated version, along with basic country information and useful links.

Figure 3: Status of MPS Platform in Europe (September 2020)

3.2.2 Country information

Wind energy zones (onshore)

In **Belgium**, wind energy zoning differs between Wallonia and Flanders. In both regions, typically a provincial wind plan outlines where and how wind projects can integrate into the landscape to achieve renewable energy targets. However, these plans are not legally binding.

In **Denmark**, onshore wind turbines are typically located in areas designated through municipal planning, adhering to specific guidelines and reservations outlined in the municipal plan. Municipalities are obliged to integrate wind turbine location planning into their development strategies by identifying and allocating areas suitable for such installations. A spatial map by the Danish government provides guidance on potential areas for wind energy development (Plan- og Landdistriktsstyrelsen and Energistyrelsen, 2024).

In **Germany**, the responsibility for determining the specific locations for suitable areas lies with its sixteen **federal states**. With the Wind-on-Land Act (2022), which came into force in February 2023, the German government set a goal to allocate 1.4% of its land area for wind energy development by the end of 2027 and 2% by the end of 2032. The Act underscores Germany's

commitment to meeting the EU's requirement to designate Renewables Acceleration Areas by February 2026.

According to a report by the German Ministry of Economics and Environment (BMWK, 2023), by December 2022 the designated areas covered between 0.81 and 0.89% of Germany's land area (variations due to incomplete GIS data). The progress on land designation is highly heterogeneous across the country. While most northern states have either met or are close to meeting their 2027 targets, many others still fall significantly behind (BMWK, 2023).

In **Italy**, on 3 July 2024, the Ministerial Decree 21 June 2024, known as the Decree on Eligible Areas, came into effect (Gazzetta Ufficiale, 2024). This decree aims to distribute the national 2030 renewable energy target. It establishes common principles and criteria for identifying suitable and unsuitable areas for renewable energy installations. Regions are required to present these designated areas, referred to as "aree idonee", by January 2025.

In the **Netherlands**, regional renewable energy strategies are being developed by thirty regions with one aim being the identification of suitable areas for renewable energy. The first version of these strategies was submitted in 2021 (Nationaal Programma RES, 2022) and is updated every two years. The latest version, published in July 2023 (Nationaal Programma RES, 2023), states that the specifics regarding wind energy areas are still under development.

In **Austria**, six out of nine **federal states** have introduced wind energy zones for onshore wind energy development: Burgenland (Austria Federal Chancellery, 2023), Lower Austria (Austria Federal Chancellery, 2014), Styria (Austria Federal Chancellery, 2024) and Salzburg (Land Salzburg, 2022). Not all of them are legally binding, however. In turn, Carinthia (Austria Federal Chancellery, 2016) and Upper Austria (Land Oberösterreich, 2017) have defined exclusion zones.

In **Portugal**, there is no nationwide designation of specific suitability zones for onshore wind energy. Instead, the country employs a general framework guiding wind project development, considering factors such as environmental impact, land use, and grid connectivity (Bucha and Ramirez Caramo, 2024). The permitting procedures involves multiple authorities, including local municipalities and national agencies, to ensure that wind farms are appropriately sited.

In **Switzerland**, the Swiss Energy Act (2016) requires cantons to designate suitable areas for wind and hydropower in their structural plans. To support cantons in this process, the Swiss government provides several resources, including the Wind Energy Concept, updated in 2020 (Federal Assembly of the Swiss Confederation, 2020), the Leaflet Wind Energy (Federal Assembly of the Swiss Confederation, 2022), and the Swiss Wind Energy Atlas (Bundesamt für Energie, 2019), which includes maps indicating zones of federal interests (such as protected natural areas, military zones or air traffic zones), where the construction of wind turbines is particularly challenging.

In April 2019, the **Norwegian** Directorate of Water Resources and Energy published a map (NVE, 2019) identifying thirteen areas it considered best suited for wind power development. During the 2019 public consultation, feedback was collected from ministries, municipalities, nature conservation associations, and other stakeholders (Olje-og energidepartementet, 2019). In response to significant criticism, the government decided to disregard the proposed areas (Olje-og energidepartementet, 2020) but committed to continuing to update the knowledge base on the effects of wind power.

In the **United Kingdom**, the identification of suitable zones for onshore wind energy development is managed through local development plans or supplementary planning documents. As of July 2024, the UK government has revised planning policies to streamline the approval process for onshore wind projects, removing specific tests that previously applied solely to these developments. This policy shift aims to place onshore wind applications on equal footing with other energy projects, potentially leading to a more flexible approach in determining suitable areas for wind energy installations (UK government, 2024).

The **Welsh** government has identified ten "pre-assessed areas" for onshore wind energy in a spatial map (Welsh Government, 2021). In this map, national parks and areas of outstanding natural beauty are deemed unsuitable for large-scale wind and solar projects.

The **Scottish** Government updated its planning policy in February 2023 through National Planning Framework 4, expressing support for new and re-powered wind farms (Scottish Government, 2023). However, the Framework emphasises that proposals for wind farms in national parks and national

scenic areas will not be supported. Additionally, the Scottish Government provides a Wind Turbine Spatial Framework dataset, which includes areas with potential for wind farm development (Scottish Government, 2024).

In **Northern Ireland**, onshore wind energy development is guided by strategic planning frameworks rather than designated zones. Key documents include “Wind Energy Development in Northern Ireland’s Landscapes” (Northern Ireland Environment Agency, 2010), which assesses the sensitivity of Landscape Character Areas, and the “Wind Map for Northern Ireland” (Department for the Economy, 2015), which identifies areas with significant wind resources to support economically viable projects.

Wind energy zones (offshore)

In **Belgium**, the federal government has delineated two specific zones for offshore wind energy development in its Marine Spatial Plan (MSP). The most recent, the Princess Elisabeth Zone, encompasses approximately 285 square kilometres. Within this zone, Belgium plans to construct an artificial energy island, the Princess Elisabeth Island, which will serve as a clean energy hub capable of handling up to 3.5 GW of offshore wind power (Norton Role Fulbright, 2024). Notably, parts of this wind energy zone are situated within existing **Nature 2000** areas.

In **Denmark**, the Danish Energy Agency discontinued the open-door scheme for coastal waters in February 2023, restricting new offshore projects to areas designated by the government. These areas are developed through a competitive tendering process. Site selection is based on a screening conducted by the Energy Agency and the Maritime Authority, which includes an economic ranking of potential locations, factoring in wind conditions and sea depth (Inquiry Commission on Offshore Wind Power, 2023).

The Danish Maritime Spatial Plan defines four zone types, including development zones for renewable energy. Renewable energy zones, designated, are binding and restrict offshore wind permits to these specific areas. The spatial map is accessible online (Danish Maritime Authority, 2023), with the latest Maritime Spatial Plan published in 2023 (Sofartsstyrelsen, 2023).

In **Germany**, the Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency designates offshore wind areas. The Network Agency awards suitable offshore wind areas to project developers through auctions. The Maritime Spatial Plans in

Germany are binding. Offshore wind power can only be developed in the designed areas. The plans for the territorial sea are decided by each coastal federal state (Inquiry Commission on Offshore Wind Power, 2023).

In **Italy**, while specific zones dedicated to offshore wind energy have not been formally established, there is significant interest in developing such projects. The country inaugurated its first offshore wind farm, Beleolico, in Taranto, with a capacity of 30 MW (International Trade Administration, 2023). Additionally, numerous grid connection requests for offshore wind projects have been submitted, indicating a growing focus on this sector (Aurora Energy Research, 2023).

In the **Netherlands**, the government has proactively identified specific zones for offshore wind energy development. The Offshore Wind Energy Roadmap by the Netherlands Enterprise Agency (2024a) outlines the locations and timelines for new wind farms, providing certainty for stakeholders. By the end of 2032, the Government wants to have 21 GW of offshore wind energy. From 2033 on, the Government aims to designate sites for the construction of new wind farms (Netherlands Enterprise Agency, 2024b).

Portugal has initiated steps towards defining of offshore wind energy zones. A public consultation in January 2023 identified three areas in the North Atlantic Ocean, totalling 3.5 GW: Viana do Castelo (1 GW), Leixões (500 MW) and Figueira da Foz (2 GW) (Donn, 2023). The first tender was launched in November 2023, with fifty bidders expressing interest (Durakovic, 2023).

In **Norway**, the right to exploit renewable energy resources at sea is vested in the state (lovdata, 2023). The King-in-Council (meetings of the King and the Cabinet) plays a vital role in offshore wind energy development, as it can designate specific areas for renewable energy construction and open them for licensing after a Strategic Environmental Impact Assessment has been conducted (lovdata, 2023).

In January 2013, the Norwegian Government conducted a Strategic Environmental Impact Assessment (NVE, 2013), analysing 15 areas in Norwegian waters. In June 2020, the Norwegian Government decided to open the first two offshore wind energy zones tender for applications (energidepartementet, 2020) and expressed plans to open additional zones in the future.

In the **United Kingdom**, many decisions and plans for offshore wind power are made by the devolved authorities of England, Wales, Scotland, and North Ireland in their respective territories. However, on a systemic level, these processes largely mirror those in England (Inquiry Commission on Offshore Wind Power, 2023). The Crown Estate owns extensive seabed areas and much of the coastline around England, Wales and Northern Ireland. It identifies specific areas for offshore wind energy and leases them to developers through competitive tendering processes. The identification of suitable areas is based on an assessment of optimal production conditions and minimal opposing interests (Inquiry Commission on Offshore Wind Power, 2023).

3.2.3 Synthesis of results

Wind energy zones (onshore)

Onshore wind energy zoning varies widely across European countries, with approaches ranging from strict legislative frameworks to voluntary regional planning strategies. Some nations, like **Germany** and **Denmark**, have established binding regulations to define and manage wind zones, while others, such as **Italy**, leave zoning decisions to regional authorities. The designation of onshore wind zones often involves balancing technical, environmental, and social considerations to maximise suitability while minimising conflict with local stakeholders.

Table 2: Wind energy suitability zones (onshore) in ten countries

Country	Description	Legally binding
Belgium		
- Wallonia	Provinces identify suitable wind energy areas (landscape)	no
- Flanders	Provinces identify suitable wind energy areas (landscape)	no
Denmark	Special map by government provides guidance to detect areas; municipalities must integrate wind areas in local planning	yes
Germany	2% goal by 2030; federal states must designate zones	yes
Italy	regions must identify zones to reach national energy targets	yes
Netherlands	thirty regions aim to identify suitable areas for renewable energy; specifics regarding wind energy areas still under development	no
Austria		
- Burgenland	Wind energy zones exist	yes
- Lower Austria	Wind energy zones exist	yes
- Styria	Wind energy zones exist	yes
- Salzburg	Areas for potential wind energy development	no
- Vorarlberg	Areas for potential wind energy development	no
- Carinthia	Wind energy exclusion zones exist	yes
- Upper Austria	Wind energy exclusion zones exist	yes
Portugal	No nationwide designation of specific suitability zones	n/a

Switzerland	cantons must designate suitable areas for wind and hydropower in their structural plans; online map helps to identify them	yes
Norway	Thirteen wind energy zones identified	no
United Kingdom		
- England	planning through local development plans (no formal zones)	no
- Wales	government identified "pre-assessed areas"	no
- Scotland	Areas for wind energy development defined	no
- Northern Ireland	Areas unsuitable for development defined	no

When designing wind energy zones, Natura 2000, the EU’s network of protected areas established to safeguard valuable and threatened species and habitats, plays a significant role as well. It covers approximately 18% of the EU's land area and nearly 9% of its marine territory (European Environmental Agency, 2022). The European Commission has provided guidance to harmonise wind energy development with the conservation objectives of Natura 2000, emphasising that such projects are not inherently excluded but must undergo thorough assessments to prevent adverse effects on protected habitats and species (European Commission, 2020).

Table 3 offers an overview of national practices governing wind energy development with respect to Natura 2000 areas. Switzerland, Norway, and the United Kingdom are not part of the Natura 2000 network and excluded from the table.

Table 3: Wind energy exclusion zones (onshore) in seven countries

Country	Description
Belgium	
- Wallonia	administration systematically refuses installations within
- Flanders	project was built in the Waaslandhaven (Natura 2000 area)
Denmark	Developers have the burden of proof of demonstrating that the basis for categorisation as a Natura 2000 site is not put at risk
Germany	In practice impossible to build within these areas
Italy	usually considered as unsuitable (developers fear lengthy procedures)
Netherlands	possible to build inside (however, developers fear lengthy procedures)
Austria	The part of one wind farm is inside such an area; in practice, however almost impossible to do so
Portugal	In theory, possible to develop a project within

Wind energy zones (offshore)

Offshore wind energy zones are increasingly defined by government-led spatial planning, which prioritises optimal wind resources and minimal environmental impact. Many EU Member States rely on comprehensive Marine Spatial Plans (MSP), designating specific areas for offshore wind

development through competitive tendering processes. Typically, Natura 2000 areas play a central role in these MSP. While many countries exclude the possibility of designating wind energy zones within a marine Natura 2000 site, examples of countries having done just so, exist.

Table 4: Wind energy suitability zones (offshore) in ten countries

Country	Description
Belgium	Federal Government has identified specific zones
Denmark	Federal Government has identified specific zones
Germany	Federal Government has identified specific zones
Italy	No offshore wind energy zones
Netherlands	Federal Government has identified specific zones
Portugal	Federal Government has identified specific zones
Norway	King-in-Council has identified specific zones
United Kingdom	Crown Estate has identified specific zones

3.3 Measures restricting wind energy development

3.3.1 Setback distances to residential areas

Setback distances to residential areas are a key consideration in the European wind energy sector. Unlike setback distances for other types of infrastructure (see Section 3.3.2), those to residential areas are often shaped more by political considerations and efforts to appease local communities than by rigorous risk assessment. This statement has been confirmed by several interviewees. In some countries, however, noise regulations play a decisive role in determining the minimum distance between residential area and wind turbines, with setback distances themselves serving as a secondary factor (Section 3.3.4).

Summarising the setback distances(see overview in **Annex A**), it can be noted that some countries use absolute numbers to define setback distances, while others opt multiplying the tip high with a certain factor. Given the increasing turbine height due to evolving technology, calculating the setback distance relative to the turbine height seems reasonable, to take into account very large turbines which cause stronger emissions, reaching farther distances. Conversely, the use of smaller turbines, typically used by local communities, might be apt to strict distance rules despite their low emission risk.

Further, setback distances to residential areas vary significantly across Europe, further supporting the assertion that these figures are often shaped

more by political rationale than risk assessment considerations. For example, the minimum distance in the federal state of Bremen, Germany, and the Flemish region in Belgium is as low as 250 m metres, whereas in Bavaria, Germany, it can extend to as much as ten times the turbine's tip.

3.3.2 Setback distances to selected types of infrastructure onshore

Setback distances to key infrastructure such as motorways, transmission lines, and railway lines, are a critical component of wind energy planning, addressing safety, operational, and environmental concerns. According to an interviewee, a common rule of thumb for calculating the safety distance is to multiply the turbine tip height by a factor of 1.2. However, specific factors such as elevation (longer shadows in elevated areas), location (higher probability of ice-throw in colder regions), wind direction, and proximity to existing infrastructure can significantly affect the calculation and the resulting setback distance.

The rationale for setback distances varies depending on the type of infrastructure. For motorways and railway lines typically, the primary goals are to ensure drivers are not distracted or "hypnotised" by the movement of wind turbine blades and to provide safety from ice-throw during colder seasons. Setback distances to transmission lines and radar systems, such as those near airports, are designed to avoid interference with electromagnetic waves. Additionally, wind turbine vibrations can disrupt sensitive nuclear monitoring systems, necessitating greater distances from military zones and testing sites.

These examples represent only a fraction of the many factors influencing wind park development. Some considerations, such as Norway's "cabin culture", are region-specific, and are thus not included in the general table in Annex B. In Norway, recreational mountain cabins often complicate turbine placement due to strong opposition from owners.

Another challenge several countries are facing involves military radar systems, which are often undisclosed for security reasons. In Germany, for example, cases have arisen where wind energy projects planned for over a year have been halted due to conflicts with military radar, underscoring the tension between state security and the need for a rapid energy transition.

Given the number of obstacles and the urgent need to expand wind energy development, the solution may not always involve increasing setback distances but addressing the obstructing object itself. Interviewees noted that it is not uncommon to install a more advanced radar system in a different location to resolve potential conflicts with wind turbines.

Annex B provides an overview of setback distances to key infrastructure, including motorways, transmission lines, railway lines, airport and radars and military zones. The findings reveal that in most cases, a specific formula must be applied to determine the distance, rather than relying on absolute values such as those used for residential areas. Interviewees highlighted that strict setback distances can pose challenges to wind energy development, reinforcing the need for flexible, case-by-case assessments.

At the same time, some interviewees expressed concerns that proving compliance with the “state of the art” requirements has become unnecessarily complex and could be demonstrated through much simpler methods. Further, norms are typically national and not harmonised. As the wind energy industry has evolved rapidly, a thorough review and consolidation of existing regulations have not occurred, leading to an increasingly burdensome demand for documentation. Streamlined and more efficient processes are therefore strongly preferred to reduce administrative hurdles and facilitate development.

3.3.3 Setback distances to selected types of infrastructure offshore

Many countries have established wind energy zones to coordinate offshore development effectively. In this context, absolute minimum distances to coastlines are rare and typically determined by factors such as the presence of tourism, residential areas near the shoreline, water depth, and other site-specific considerations.

For instance, the high cost of constructing fixed wind turbines in deep waters often limits their placement. Portugal, however, focuses on floating wind turbines, which, due to their nature, are typically located around 20 kilometres from the shore. In contrast, examples from countries like Denmark and Norway illustrate turbines positioned so close to shore that they remain partially submerged to high tide and are exposed at low tide, showcasing the diversity in offshore siting strategies.

When defining wind energy zones, additional factors must also be taken into account, including the presence of shipping routes, fishing areas, underwater cables, pipelines and other marine infrastructure.

The concept of addressing the obstacle itself, rather than increasing the setback distances, as discussed in Section 3.3.2, is equally relevant to offshore wind energy. In 2024, the German marine authority announced a significant realignment of shipping routes to accommodate an additional 10 GW of offshore wind energy capacity, demonstrating a proactive approach to balancing maritime navigation with renewable energy expansion (BSH, 2024).

A comparable example pertains to fishing areas, where, for example in Denmark, fishing areas must sometimes give way to other legally permissible uses, such as offshore wind energy development. In such cases, fishermen are typically entitled to compensation for future loss of earnings, ensuring a fair resolution to competing interests (Deutscher Bundestag, 2018).

However, certain obstacles, such as underwater cables and pipelines, are not economically feasible to relocate. Against this background, Germany's 2023 Marine Spatial Plan, for instance, mandates a minimum distance of 100 – 500 metres from underwater cables and 50 metres from pipelines to ensure operational safety and infrastructure protection (BSH, 2023).

3.3.4 Noise limits

Noise limits for onshore wind energy are regulated across Europe to balance wind energy development with community well-being. Many countries adopt stricter limits at night to protect residents' sleep quality, while others also consider background noise levels or adjust thresholds based on wind speed, housing type or area (e.g. residential or industrial zone). Most Member States set noise limits for wind turbines within a range of 45 to 55 dB (daytime) and 35 to 45 dB (nighttime). In addition, certain countries, such as Denmark, also measure low frequency noise, which is limited to 20 dB at wind speeds of 6 and 8 metres per second both in residential and housing in rural areas.

In 2010, the Dutch government opted for the use of $L(\text{den})$ and $L(\text{night})$ for the assessment of wind turbine noise, in accordance with the definition in the European Environmental Noise Directive. However, this is no obligation since the Directive does not apply to wind turbines. $L(\text{den})$ and $L(\text{night})$ are

based on annual averaged sound levels. None of the other seven countries studied use annual averaged sound levels to regulate wind turbine noise. These countries use the equivalent sound pressure level L(Aeq), a parameter based on the equivalent sound level or a statistical parameter for the assessment of wind turbine noise. In Europe, besides the Netherlands only Norway uses the parameter L(den) for regulating wind turbine noise.

Table 5: Noise limits to residential areas in ten countries

Country	Residential areas		Housing in rural areas		additional information
	day limit (max.)	night limit (max.)	day limit (max.)	night limit (max.)	
Belgium					
- Flanders	44 dB(A)	39 dB(A)	48 dB(A)	43 dB(A)	area + time
- Wallonia	43 dB(A)	43 dB(A)	like residential areas		time
Denmark	42 dB(A) at 6 m/sec. 44 dB(A) at 8 m/sec.		37 dB(A) at 6 m/sec. 39 dB(A) at 8 m/sec.		area + wind speed
Germany	50 dB(A)	35/40 dB(A)	60 dB(A)	45 dB(A)	area + time
Italy	55 dB	45 dB	???		area + time
Netherlands	47 dB(Lden)	41 dB(Lnight)	like residential areas		area + time
Austria	45 dB	45 dB	40 dB	40 dB	background noise level (BNL)
Portugal	55 dB	45 dB	???		area + time
Switzerland	55 dB	45 dB	50 dB	40 dB	area + time
Norway	45 dB(Lden)		49 dB(Lden)		area + time
United Kingdom	BNL + 5 dB(A) or 35 - 40 dB(A)	BNL + 5 dB(A) or 43 dB(A)	like residential areas		background noise level (BNL)

3.3.5 Shadow flicker

Shadow flicker is a phenomenon that occurs when the rotating blades of a wind turbine cast moving shadows, causing a flickering effect as they pass over openings like windows or doors. This can be a concern for nearby residents, as the intermittent light and shadow can be disruptive.

In general, shadow flicker standards are more uniform than noise standards. In 2002, Germany published a guideline for calculating and assessing shadow flicker, based on scientific research. As shown in Table 6, most countries that have a regulation or a guideline for assessing shadow flicker based this on the German guideline (Koppen and Ekelschot-Smink, 2023).

The German guideline, updated in 2019, sets a shadow flicker limit of 30 hours per year or 30 minutes per day for the astronomical maximum possible shadow duration (worst-case scenario) (LAI, 2020). If a shadow flicker control system is used which automatically stalls the wind turbine at times shadow flicker is expected to occur, the actual shadow flicker duration must be limited to 8 hours per year.

Table 6: Shadow flicker in ten countries

Country	hours/year	minutes/day	other information
Belgium			
- Flanders	8	30	regulation
- Wallonia	30	30	regulation
Denmark	10	-	-
Germany	30	30	guideline
Italy	N/A	N/A	typically, 30/30
Netherlands	17 days	20	most deviating shadow flicker; currently under revision due to court verdict
Austria	30	30	guideline
Portugal	N/A	N/A	could nonetheless be condition for obtaining permit
Switzerland	30	30	-
Norway	8	30	guideline
United Kingdom	N/A	N/A	typically, 30/30

3.4 Financial participation and compensation schemes

3.4.1 General information

Literature review

Research indicates that financial compensation is an effective tool for increasing local acceptance of wind energy projects (Knauf, 2022; Vuichard et al., 2019). These mechanisms may include providing affected stakeholders with fixed financial compensation or offering them a share in the wind park through financial participation schemes (financial participation). As one German mayor described it, financial participation schemes ensure that “everybody profits from the cake” (NDR, 2024).

Financial participation schemes for wind energy projects vary across Europe in several aspects: the type of participation (e.g., wind energy shares or pre-set payments), the calculation formula for compensation (e.g., per wind turbine or per MW/year), the group of beneficiaries (e.g., municipalities or citizens), and the compensation amount itself. For example, compensation is EUR 3,000 per installed MW/year in Burgenland, Austria, compared to EUR

5,000 in Brandenburg, Germany⁴. Building on these differences, de Luca et al. (2020) identified six distinct types of **financial participation** (see Table 7).

Table 7: Types of financial participation models proposed by de Luca et al. (2020)

Financial Participation Type	Practical Example
(1) individual direct	issuing wind energy shares (with voting rights) to citizens near a wind park
(2) individual indirect	issuing wind energy shares (without voting rights) to citizens near a wind park
(3) communal direct	issuing wind energy shares (with voting rights) to municipalities near a wind park
(4) communal indirect	issuing wind energy shares (without voting rights) to municipalities near a wind park
(5) individual passive	transferring pre-set compensation payments to individual citizens near the wind park
(6) communal passive	transferring pre-set compensation payments to municipalities near the wind park ("wind energy fund")

Wind energy shares: Not everybody can afford them

Recent developments show that citizens desire to benefit adequately from favourable years in the renewable energy sector. For instance, the significant profits generated during the winter of 2022/23, following the Russian invasion of Ukraine, sparked a public debate about the need for an excess profit tax on energy companies (BMF, 2022; Nicolay et al., 2023). To enhance distributional justice in the wind energy sector, a financial participation law could mandate wind park companies to offer profit-based compensation, rather than pre-set payments, ensuring that compensation reflects annual profits generated.

However, issuing wind energy shares poses the challenge that less-affluent citizens may lack the financial means to purchase them. For example, Denmark implemented the "Purchase Right Scheme" in 2008, requiring wind park companies to offer at least 20% of the project's ownership shares to citizens and municipalities near the wind park (Leer Jørgensen et al., 2020; Szabo, 2020). Despite this initiative, reports from the Danish Energy Agency (2011) highlight low citizen participation and the emergence of "wind energy nomads" – investors who buy property near a wind park solely to qualify for

⁴ This number derives the revised version of the Brandenburg financial participation law, which will be adopted in 2024/25.

share purchases. Researchers have also noted that few shares are acquired in Danish wind parks (Leer Jørgensen et al., 2020), reasons including a lack of capital (Johansen and Emborg, 2018; Kirch Kirkegaard et al., 2021; Lienhoop, 2018), awareness (Leer Jørgensen et al., 2020), and trust and knowledge (Langer et al., 2017; Leer Jørgensen et al., 2020).

Given the challenge of promoting wind energy shares among a broad range of residents, researchers suggest that policymakers consider other forms of financial participation, such as direct compensation of municipalities or residents with a pre-set amount (Lienhoop, 2018; Vuichard et al., 2019). In 2019, the Danish government announced a shift in strategy, requiring wind park companies to provide such pre-set payments to residents instead (Danish Energy Agency, 2019). New renewable energy schemes, replacing the Purchase Right Scheme, came into force in June 2020 (Energistyrelsen, 2019).

Financial mechanisms to empower everyone to become a shareholder

However, the replacement of the Purchase Right Scheme in Denmark warrants critical consideration for two reasons. First, it eliminates the opportunity for residents to gain co-ownership in the wind parks and to profit from economically favourable years. Guaranteeing that all citizens have an equitable opportunity to participate in the energy transition, regardless of financial means, is essential not only to achieving the EU's goal of a "just" and "inclusive" energy transition (European Parliament and Council, 2021a), but also to fostering local acceptance of renewable energy projects (Holstenkamp, 2019).

Second, it overlooks existing financing mechanisms, such as the one proposed by Kelso (Kelso and Kelso, 1989) which has proven effective in enabling less-affluent citizens to use the future earnings of a company share to repay the acquisition loan for that share. This model, commonly known as Employee Stock Ownership Plans (ESOPs) in corporate settings, could be adapted to the renewable energy sector to democratise financial participation. By allowing citizens to gradually repay their investment with dividends generated by the wind park, this approach eliminates significant financial barriers and encourages broader participation. Relevant work in this area includes Lowitzsch's development of the Consumer Stock Ownership Plan (CSOP), which enables energy consumers to become stakeholders in an energy firm (Lowitzsch, 2019).

Wind energy compensation payments: How are they being invested?

Systematic research on how municipalities in Europe utilise wind energy compensation payments remain scarce. Similarly, there is limited data on whether, and to what extent, citizens are involved in deciding which projects should be financed with these payments. This lack of information may be attributed to the recent implementation of many financial participation laws in many European states. Furthermore, many financial participation models rely on a voluntary agreement, making it more challenging to collect comprehensive public data.

In Germany, municipalities like of Fohren-Linden in Rhineland-Palatinate (SWR, 2023) and Bokum in Lower Saxony (NDR, 2024) have utilised wind energy compensation payments for various community projects. In Fohren-Linden, these funds have been allocated to construct a playground (EUR 40,000), renovate a bus stop (EUR 100,000), update the town hall kitchen (EUR 30,000) and reduce the property tax, which benefits property owners. Similarly, Bokum has used compensation payments to support the continued operation of its public swimming pool.

One potential investment area for compensation payments is the development of a decentralised energy system. While the EU's Clean Energy Package (European Commission, 2023d) and its announcement to "shift from centralised [...] to decentralised" energy generation as well as to empower consumers to "generate their energy" raised hopes for an inclusive energy transition high, a study by Schwanitz et al. (2023) revealed that only about 0.004% of the EU population actively participates in this transition. The main barriers to achieving a just transition, even seven years after the Clean Energy Package, remain administrative challenges (Frieden et al., 2021) and significant financing gaps (Pons-Seres de Brauwer and Cohen, 2020).

Wind energy money: Who should choose the investment projects?

In Germany, federal states have begun recognising the potential of wind energy compensation payments to support a more decentralised energy transition, actively encouraging municipalities to invest the "wind energy money" received to optimise energy costs and consumption (Landtag Mecklenburg Vorpommern, 2016; Landtag Nordrhein-Westfalen, 2024; Landtag Saarland, 2024; Landtag Sachsen, 2024; Landtag Thüringen, 2024). However, the broad wording used in the various financial participation laws of the federal states provides municipalities with significant leeway in

determining how these payments are invested. The only binding requirement is that the investments must be designed to enhance “local acceptance” of wind energy projects.

With respect to increasing local acceptance, studies suggest that the process of selecting projects is as important as the projects’ content, with local authorities encouraged to actively involve citizens in the decision-making process (le Maitre et al., 2023, 2024a). However, a significant research gap remains regarding this type of citizen involvement. While numerous studies explore financial participation schemes that require wind park operators to transfer compensation payments directly to municipalities – often noting a preference among citizens for this approach over direct payments to individuals (Knauf, 2022; Lienhoop, 2018; Vuichard et al., 2022, 2019) – they fail to address how the municipality should govern and allocate the compensation payments once received.

Only a few studies have critically examined the administration of wind energy compensation payments (Cass et al., 2010) or analysed local opinions on this subject (le Maitre et al., 2024b, 2023). Research by le Maitre et al. (le Maitre et al., 2024b, 2023) reveals that Irish citizens prefer a citizen committee, rather than the local authority, to govern the accrued compensation payments. In light of this, le Maitre et al. (2024b) propose that justice elements should be incorporated in financial participation laws, to ensure that citizens can propose how the contributions should be used. Actively involving citizens in the decision-making not only strengthens democratic procedural structures but also ensures investments align with local interests, thereby reducing the risk of conflicts.

The potential of "Local Action Groups"

To address the challenge of insufficient citizen participation, the EU actively promotes and supports "**Community-Led Local Development**" and the establishment of "**Local Action Groups**" (European Parliament and Council, 2021b). These groups are tasked with drafting and managing local development strategies and applying for EU funding, for example, to purchase renewable energy assets or install Smart Energy Systems (European Parliament and Council, 2021b). Notably, the costs for establishing and managing Local Action Groups are covered, irrespective of whether their strategy is ultimately selected (European Parliament and Council, 2021b).

If a Local Action Group is established following EU guidelines (European Parliament and Council, 2021b), it could also be tasked with designing strategies for investing (parts of) the wind energy compensation payments received by the municipality. Due to its inclusive membership structure, it is reasonable to assume that the projects selected by the Local Action Group would align closely with local interests.

If planned strategically, municipalities could benefit from three additional income streams: (1) EU funding⁵ for establishing a Local Action Group; (2) EU funding⁶ to support the local energy transition; and (3) energy savings achieved through the creation of a local energy community and the acquisition of renewable energy assets.

3.4.2 Country information

In the Flemish region of **Belgium**, there is no specific legislation promoting private shareholding in wind turbine projects. In contrast, in Wallonia, the government introduced a framework in 2013 to address the decline in new wind energy projects since 2011, which was partly due to an increase in legal challenges. This framework requires wind energy developers to allocate 24.99% of the capital of each new project to citizen participation and 24.99% to municipal participation (Le Ministre de l'Environnement, de l'Aménagement du territoire et de la Mobilité, 2013).

In **Denmark**, households located within a distance of four to eight times the turbine height from the nearest wind producing at least 5,000 MWh annually can receive compensation of up to DKK 285 per MW of capacity directly (approximately EUR 38) under the "Bonus Scheme" (Klima-, Energi- og Forsyningsministeriet, 2024a).

Additionally, the "Green Fund Scheme" requires renewable energy plants owners to pay a lump sum to a fund administered by the municipality where the plant is installed. The payment equals DKK 313,000 per MW (approximately EUR 42,000) for onshore wind turbines and DKK 418,000 per MW (approximately EUR 56,000) for offshore wind turbines (Klima-, Energi- og

⁵ Art. 31 *ibid*: [...] the ERDF, the ESF+, the JTF and the EMFAF shall support community-led local development.

⁶ Annex I *ibid*: ERDF, the ESF+, the Cohesion Fund and the JTF.

Forsyningsministeriet, 2024b). The fund is allocated to benefit the local community (Klima-, Energi- og Forsyningsministeriet, 2024a).

The Danish Energy Agency (2024) has published a guidance document detailing how municipalities should administer the Green Scheme fund. Similar to the Community-Led Local Development approach (Section 3.4.1.), the Agency instructs municipalities to allocate funding based on applications submitted by residents (living within a distance of six times the turbine height). Notably, the municipalities themselves are not eligible to apply for the fund. Instead, project applications are evaluated for relevance and impact, ensuring transparency in the allocation process.

In **Germany**, since 2021, a national regulation permits wind park operators to compensate affected municipalities with **up to** 0.2 cents per kWh electricity sold to the grid (Deutsches Bundesministerium der Justiz, 2021). This regulation was introduced following allegations of corruption involving public authorities, some of which led to court proceedings. By legalising such compensation, the regulation exempts these payments from legal penalties.

Federal states have the authority to establish their own financial participation rules. As of 2024, nine federal states have exercised this option (Bundesverband WindEnergie, 2024), with the most recent draft proposal presented by the Bavarian government (2024). Of these, only three states – Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania (2016), North Rhine-Westphalia (2024) and Lower Saxony (2024) – explicitly encourage wind park operators to offer projects shares to shareholders.

In this context, the municipality of **Hoort** in Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania is a noteworthy example. In 2020, 16 wind turbines were constructed in the municipality. Instead of acquiring the 20% project shares outlined in the federal law, Hoort opted to acquire 25% even. The revenues generated from the wind farm have been used for projects such as renovating the community centre and operating the local daycare. This approach has fostered a strong sense of identification among Hoort's residents with "their" wind farm (Deutsch-Französisches Zukunftswerk, 2023).

In addition, several states have developed advanced online maps to display accrued wind energy compensation funds. Figure 4 shows an excerpt of Brandenburg's wind energy map, where hovering over the municipality of Karstädt reveals that it had accrued EUR 87,196 by 2024.

Figure 4: Map of Brandenburg indicating magnitude of financial participation

In **Italy**, there is no national legislation requiring wind park operators to offer financial participation or compensation to affected citizens or municipalities. However, such obligations may be imposed by regional regulations or agreements.

In the **Netherlands**, financial compensation for wind energy projects is not mandated by law. Nonetheless, to promote acceptance, project developers provide voluntary financial contributions, with the allocation of funds partly determined through dialogue with the local community. As a general guideline, a contribution of €0.40 to €0.50 per MWh is commonly applied (2020). The Dutch Climate Agreement also sets a goal of 50% local ownership in large-scale renewable electricity generation projects on land (above 15 kW). This goes beyond just financial participation, encompassing decision-making rights. Local stakeholders, including citizens, become co-owner of the project and automatically benefit from the proceeds (Rijksdienst voor Ondernemend Nederland, 2024).

In **Austria**, only the federal state of Burgenland mandates wind park operators to compensate affected stakeholders (Government of Burgenland, 2023). Operators must pay EUR 3,000 per installed MW of capacity, split equally between the hosting municipality and the federal state. Notably, this law is, introduced in June 2023, applies not only to new wind farms but also includes a scheme to gradually incorporate wind farms constructed before that law's announcement, unlike similar legislation in Germany. Currently,

the federal government is working on a unified financial compensation scheme draft.

In **Portugal**, wind farms under the feed-in-tariff system must allocate 2.5% of revenues to municipalities. For new projects, developers pay EUR 1,500 per MVA of installed capacity, and an additional EUR 13,5 per MVA is contributed by the Environmental Fund under the Resilience and Recovery Plan (Diário da República Portuguesa, 2022). Developers are also required to implement local projects to promote energy efficiency or self-consumption in affected municipalities

In **Switzerland**, there is no standard compensation scheme, but it is common practice for developers to negotiate compensation directly with municipalities. The terms of such agreements vary by project. Additionally, since 1918, a special annual tax known as “Wasserzins” has been levied on hydro park operators for using water resources (Schweizerischer Wasserwirtschaftsverband, 2023). The proceeds from this tax benefit both the hosting canton and the affected municipalities (Schweizer Bundesamt für Energie, 2023).

Effective from 1 January 2024, the **Norwegian** Government introduced a resource rent tax on onshore wind power, applicable to wind farms with more than five turbines or with a total installed capacity of 1 MW or more, at an effective tax rate of 25% - 10% lower than the government’s initial proposal (pwc, 2023; The Norwegian Ministry of Finance, 2023). A significant portion of the tax revenues is allocated to host municipalities, ensuring they receive a fair share of the value generated from local wind resources.

In the **United Kingdom**, there is no standard compensation scheme for wind energy projects. However, England, Wales and Scotland provide guidelines for wind park operators interested in implementing such models. In 2013, the UK government endorsed a Community Benefits Protocol for Onshore Wind in England, which encourages developers to offer packages or in-kind benefits of GBP 5,000 per MW of installed capacity per year (approximately EUR 6,000), for the operational lifetime of the project, typically 20-25 years (Department for Energy Security & Net Zero, 2024).

In 2014, the UK Government issued guidance for onshore wind farm developers, local communities, and authorities to design benefit packages

tailored to local needs. This guidance was updated in December 2021 (Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy, 2021). The updated guideline encourages wind park developers to engage in consultations with affected stakeholders regarding community benefits and outlines various compensation schemes, including community benefits funds, in-kind benefits, and shared ownership.

In March 2023, the government proposed expanding the range of community schemes to include emerging and innovative options, such as energy bill discounts for host communities. These changes aim to further involve local residents in the government's "Powering Up Britain" plan, supporting the delivery of cheaper, cleaner and more secure homegrown energy (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, 2023).

The **Welsh** government encourages developers to collaborate with local communities to determine suitable benefit packages. In 2020, it published a policy statement on local ownership of energy generation, emphasising that all new energy projects should include at least some level of local ownership to retain wealth within Wales and deliver tangible benefit to communities (Welsh Government, 2020). According to the Welsh office of RenewableUK (2023), community benefit funds related to onshore wind projects in Wales provide over GBP 6.5 million annually, based on just under 1.3 GW of operational capacity.

The **Scottish Government** recommends a standard community benefit rate of GBP 5,000 per MW of installed capacity per year (approximately EUR 6,000) and provides general guidance on community benefits from onshore wind energy development (2019). The document outlines best practices for creating benefit packages tailored to "the needs of the local community", emphasising community involvement in decision-making. Additionally, Scotland promotes community ownership of renewable energy projects, allowing communities to have a direct stake in local wind farms (House of Commons Library, 2024). Similar to the German state of Brandenburg, Scotland offers a "Community Benefits Map" (2024) that shows the financial benefits received by municipalities from wind park operators.

In **Northern Ireland**, the approach to community benefits mirrors that of England and Wales, relying on voluntary schemes developed through engagement between developers and local communities. These schemes aim to ensure that host communities receive tangible benefits, such as

community funds, educational programmes, or infrastructure improvements (House of Commons Library, 2024).

3.4.3 Synthesis of results

The synthesis of the results is presented in **ANNEX C**, offering a comprehensive overview of financial participation and compensation schemes across Europe. The provided table highlights significant variation in approaches among countries and regions. While some countries have implemented legally binding regulations mandating wind park operators to compensate municipalities and/or citizens affected by the projects, others have introduced only non-binding guidelines, and some have not addressed this issue at either federal or regional level.

4. PYTHON PACKAGE TO ESTIMATE JOB CREATION OF INDIVIDUAL WIND FARMS

The output of this task is a python package that includes two models that are defined as individual functions. Both models are derived from the job creation data from scientific literature and grey literature compiled in D2.9. The first model, function 1, is a simplified version of the model presented in D2.9. It relies on descriptive statistics of the underlying data. This was created with the aim of allowing users to easily incorporate new data that could be collected. If new data is added the multipliers the respective wind farm life stages and job types will adapt. The second model, function 2, reproduces the model presented in D2.9. Both functions produce slightly different results with the current data set. The main difference is that function 2 can take the size in MW per turbine into consideration. If no additional data is to be incorporated we recommend to use function 2, which was validated through expert interviews and comparing values of individual farms to scientific literature (see D2.9.)

The only necessary inputs for these functions are turbine capacity (only for function 2), number of turbines, country of deployment, and whether the installation is on-shore or off-shore. The models rely on Python packages such as pandas and numpy. An example of an input that can be used for model 2 is provided in Table 8:

Table 8: Input parameters for the job creation functions

Parameters and example	Description
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<ul style="list-style-type: none">- number_of_turbines = 9- turbine_capacity = 4- country = 'Italy'- onshore_offshore = 'Offshore'	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Integer representing the number of turbines- Float corresponding to the installed capacity per turbine in MW- A string containing the European country where the wind farm is located. It should be written in English.- A string that could be either "onshore" or "offshore" reflecting if there is an onshore or an off-shore farm respectively.
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It is important to note that for Function 1, using only statistics for job creation calculations, does not allow to account for the turbine capacity, as this will lead to unrealistically high values of jobs created. Running function 1 therefore only requires the parameters "turbine_capacity", "country" and "onshore_offshore".

4.1 Job creation model - Function 1

To analyse job creation in Europe for the first function, the job creation data from scientific literature and grey literature compiled in D2.9 was filtered separately for European onshore and offshore cases. However, each life stage (e.g., Development, Construction, Manufacturing, Operation & Maintenance, and Decommissioning) required specific filtering criteria, both for onshore and offshore, to ensure the data's completion. Generally, data derived from other sources (papers citing other papers that we already included in the job creation data set) was always excluded. This to avoid double accounting.

The filtering process by life stage for **onshore** was the following:

- Development: No filters were applied. All rows from the development stage were included, meaning data from the whole world was used

without differentiating onshore from offshore. This was due to the limited number of total development data points for Europe.

- Construction: Data was filtered to include only onshore data, however still using data from the whole world due to the lack of data on induced jobs for Europe.
- Manufacturing: No filters were applied. All rows from the manufacturing stage were included, meaning data from the whole world was used without differentiating onshore from offshore. This was due to the lack of data on manufacturing induced jobs for Europe.
- Operation and Maintenance: Data was filtered to include only onshore data, however still using data from the whole world due to the lack of data on O&M induced jobs for Europe.
- Decommissioning: No filters were applied. All rows from the decommissioning stage were included, meaning data from the whole world was used without differentiating onshore from offshore. This was due to the limited number of total decommissioning data points.

The filtering process by life stage for **offshore** was the following:

- Development: No filters were applied. All rows from the development stage were included, meaning data from the whole world was used without differentiating onshore from offshore. This was due to the limited number of total development data points.
- Construction: Data was filtered to include only European offshore data.
- Manufacturing: Data was filtered to include only European offshore data.
- Operation and Maintenance: Data was filtered to include only European offshore data.
- Decommissioning: No filters were applied. All rows from the decommissioning stage were included, meaning data from the whole world was used without differentiating onshore from offshore. This was due to the limited number of total decommissioning data points.

Table 9 and Table 10 show the statistics results for onshore and offshore of the simplified model used in function 1.

Table 9: Statistics results for onshore used for Function 1 (values in job-years/MW_i)

Life Stage	Statistic	Direct	Indirect	Induced	Total
Development	Maximum	1.41	1.09	0.7	2.37

	Mean	0.6925	0.586667	0.59	1.855
	Median	0.575	0.41	0.59	1.855
	Minimum	0.21	0.26	0.48	1.34
	Sample Std Dev	0.516938	0.442305	0.155563	0.72832
Construction	Maximum	10.3	4.93	9.1	9.2
	Mean	2.303806	2.001818	2.130667	3.561667
	Median	1.495	1.55	0.755	2.8975
	Minimum	0.244	0.077	0.154	0.475
	Sample Std Dev	2.312514	1.672986	3.443073	2.945204
	Maximum	22.5	16.9	4.1	39.4
	Mean	7.431583	5.684	3.65	14.77083
	Median	4.475	3.889	3.65	10.985
	Minimum	0.625	2.26	3.2	1.25
	Sample Std Dev	6.089314	4.553356	0.636396	13.08959
	Maximum	25	19.643	14.319	10
	Mean	7.939657	5.1916	4.002714	6.219
O&M	Median	6.95	2.7905	1.992	5.132
	Minimum	0.897	0.199	1	3.419
	Sample Std Dev	6.37751	5.783029	4.709867	2.629532
	Maximum	2.655	1.186	1.005	4.275
Decommissioning	Mean	1.7005	0.9005	1.005	4.275
	Median	1.7005	0.9005	1.005	4.275
	Minimum	0.746	0.615	1.005	4.275
	Sample Std Dev	1.349867	0.403758	-	-

Table 10: Statistics results for offshore used for Function 1 (values in job-years/MWi)

Life Stage	Statistic	Direct	Indirect	Induced	Total
Development	Maximum	1.41	1.09	0.7	2.37
	Mean	0.6925	0.586667	0.59	1.855
	Median	0.575	0.41	0.59	1.855
	Minimum	0.21	0.26	0.48	1.34
	Sample Std Dev	0.516938	0.442305	0.155563	0.72832
Construction	Maximum	15	11.1	7.1	44.3
	Mean	5.803286	4.0532	5.115	20.21333
	Median	4.3	2.67	5.115	8.84
	Minimum	1.48	0.95	3.13	7.5
	Sample Std Dev	4.520327	4.026256	2.807214	20.87042
Manufacturing	Maximum	22.5	16.9	4.1	39.4
	Mean	11.23283	7.59175	3.65	21.80167
	Median	9.958	5.3735	3.65	16.985
	Minimum	3.11	2.72	3.2	9.02
	Sample Std Dev	6.396374	6.453751	0.636396	15.75234
O&M	Maximum	18	14.8395	18.105	41
	Mean	7.529667	7.6257	12.24	31.83333
	Median	5	3.671	12.24	31.6

	Minimum	2.857	2.375	6.375	22.9
	Sample Std Dev	5.110205	6.058106	8.294363	9.052256
Decommissioning	Maximum	2.655	1.186	1.005	4.275
	Mean	1.7005	0.9005	1.005	4.275
	Median	1.7005	0.9005	1.005	4.275
	Minimum	0.746	0.615	1.005	4.275
	Sample Std Dev	1.349867	0.403758	-	-

4.2 Job creation model - Function 2

The second function, as described in D2.9, integrates the results of a multiple linear regression analysis with statistical data. The adapted significant regression equations that were used for individual wind farms in Europe are the following:

$$EF_{con, dir} = 9.46 - (3.65 \times OS) - (4.07)$$

$$EF_{manu, dir} = 13.37 - (9.50 \times OS)$$

$$EF_{o\&m, dir} = 19.38 + (0.92 \times TC) - (15.74)$$

$$EF_{decom, dir} = 2.82 - (2.11 \times OS)$$

Where TC is the turbine capacity in MW, and OS is a dummy variable having a value of 1 or 0 describing if the wind farm is off-shore or not.

The statistical data used in this model complements the regression equations by filling gaps where regression models could not be constructed because of the lack of data, specifically for direct development jobs, and indirect and induced jobs across all life stages. These statistics were calculated based on data for the whole world. The statistics results are presented in Table II.

Table II: Statistics results used for Function 2 (values in job-years/MWi)

Life Stage	Statistic	Direct	Indirect	Induced	Total
Development	Minimum	0.21	0.26	0.48	1.34
	Maximum	1.41	1.09	0.7	2.37
	Mean	0.6925	0.586667	0.59	1.855
	Median	0.575	0.41	0.59	1.855
	Sample Std Dev	0.516938	0.442305	0.155563	0.72832
Construction	Minimum	0.244	0.077	0.154	0.475
	Maximum	15	11.1	14.4	44.3
	Mean	3.763462	3.134222	4.157111	9.112222
	Median	2.1585	2.103	1.5	3.32
	Sample Std Dev	3.695228	2.908513	4.981779	13.55118
Manufacturing	Minimum	0.625	2.26	3.2	1.25

	Maximum	22.5	16.9	4.1	39.4
	Mean	7.431583	5.684	3.65	14.77083
	Median	4.475	3.889	3.65	10.985
	Sample Std Dev	6.089314	4.553356	0.636396	13.08959
O&M	Minimum	0.897	0.199	1	2.625
	Maximum	26.36	19.643	25.515	41
	Mean	7.059357	5.926816	7.546727	13.4715
	Median	5	3.671	4.874	7.9325
	Sample Std Dev	5.895532	5.342182	8.143783	12.59619
Decommissioning	Minimum	0.746	0.615	1.005	4.275
	Maximum	2.655	1.186	1.005	4.275
	Mean	1.7005	0.9005	1.005	4.275
	Median	1.7005	0.9005	1.005	4.275
	Sample Std Dev	1.349867	0.403758	-	-

The output of both functions is a pandas data frame providing the estimated job creation values for the considered wind farm divided by type of job (direct, indirect and induced) and stage in the lifetime of the wind farm (development, construction, manufacturing, operation and maintenance and decommissioning). An example output for Function 2 for an on-shore and an off-shore wind farm are provided in Table 12 and Table 13 respectively.

Table 12: Output example of Function 2 for an on-shore wind farm with one turbine of 5MW located in Germany (values in job-years/MWi)

Life Stage	Direct Jobs	Indirect Jobs	Induced Jobs	Total	National /International	Share (%)
Development	0.692	0.586	0.59	1.869	National	3.859
Construction	1.74	3.134	4.157	9.031	National	18.646
Manufacturing	3.87	5.684	3.65	13.204	National	27.262
O&M	8.24	5.926	7.546	21.713	National	44.831
Decommissioning	0.71	0.900	1.005	2.615	National	5.400
Total	15.252	16.232	16.948	48.43	-	100

Table 13: Output example of Function 2 for an off-shore wind farm with one turbine of 8MW located in Germany (values in job-years/MWi)

Life Stage	Direct Jobs	Indirect Jobs	Induced Jobs	Total	National /International	Share (%)
Development	0.692	0.586	0.59	1.869	National	2.812
Construction	5.39	3.134	4.157	12.681	National	19.083
Manufacturing	13.37	5.684	3.65	22.704	National	34.165
O&M	11	5.926	7.546	24.473	National	36.828
Decommissioning	2.82	0.900	1.005	4.725	National	7.110

Total	33.272	16.232	16.948	66.453	-	100
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5. CONCLUSIONS

5.1. Regulations governing wind energy development in Europe

5.1.1 Renewable Acceleration Areas can facilitate wind energy development

To address the need to streamline wind energy development, the Renewable Energy Directive (RED III) emphasises the establishment of Renewable Acceleration Areas. Many Member States have already such areas or wind energy zones. One aim of wind energy zones is to reduce legal and procedural uncertainties for developers. This fosters investor confidence and encourages investment in renewable energy infrastructure.

The designation of Renewable Acceleration Areas is based on strategic planning to identify areas with minimal environmental and social constraints, partly supported by the Energy and Industry Geography Lab of the EU and the European Marine Spatial Planning Platform. This reduces potential conflicts with protected areas, local communities, and other land uses, facilitating smoother project implementation.

The requirement for Renewable Acceleration Areas introduces a more unified approach to renewable energy planning across the EU, fostering collaboration and best practices among Member States. Additionally, they are ideally aligned with existing or planned grid infrastructure, ensuring efficient energy transmission and minimizing costs associated with grid expansion or upgrades. This is especially relevant considering the increasing grid connection and curtailment costs.

However, the introduction of Renewable Acceleration Areas or wind energy zones also comes with certain challenges. For instance, focussing on large-scale, grid-integrated projects in selected areas may marginalise small-scale or community-led wind energy initiatives, reducing opportunities for local participation. It is thus advisable to keep the option for local communities to construct a wind park in their vicinity, even if it is located outside of a dedicated area, open.

5.1.2 Dynamic preferable to absolute minimum distances

Setback distances to key infrastructure such as motorways, transmission lines, and railway lines, as well, are a critical component of wind energy planning. Our research highlights that here, typically formulas are used to calculate the setback distance (for instance, 1.2 times the tip height in Austria). Interviewees highlighted that strict setback distances can pose challenges to wind energy development, reinforcing the need for flexible, case-by-case assessments.

In addition, a case-by-case analysis is typically required as well, considering factors such as elevation (longer shadows in elevated areas), location (higher probability of ice-throw in colder regions), wind direction, and proximity to existing infrastructure can significantly affect the calculation and the resulting setback distance.

Setback distances to residential areas, in turn, are typically represented in absolute numbers rather than dynamic formulas. Our research highlights significant differences between setback distances introduced across Europe. This stringent approach can be an indicator for the fact that setback distances to residential areas are often shaped more by political considerations and efforts to appease local communities than by rigorous risk assessment. This statement has been confirmed by several interviewees.

In turn, however, interviewees also expressed concerns that proving compliance with the “state of the art” requirements has become unnecessarily complex and could be demonstrated through much simpler methods. As the wind energy industry has evolved rapidly, a thorough review and consolidation of existing regulations have not occurred, leading to an increasingly burdensome demand for documentation. Streamlined and more efficient processes are therefore strongly preferred to reduce administrative hurdles and facilitate development.

Many countries have established wind energy zones to coordinate offshore development effectively. In this context, absolute minimum distances to coastlines are rare and typically determined by factors such as the presence of tourism, residential areas near the shoreline, water depth, and other site-specific consideration. When defining wind energy zones, additional factors must also be considered, including the presence of shipping routes, fishing areas, underwater cables, pipelines and other marine infrastructure.

When it comes to shipping routes and fishing areas, examples of re-locating them exist. In such a case, fishermen are typically entitled to compensation for future loss of earnings. However, certain obstacles, such as underwater cables and pipelines, are not economically feasible to relocate. Against this background, harmonised formula calculating the setback distance to such infrastructure sounds reasonable.

5.1.3 *Financial participation schemes are effective but need a social update*

Financial participation schemes for wind energy projects vary across Europe in several aspects: the type of participation (e.g., wind energy shares or pre-set payments), the calculation formula for compensation (e.g., per wind turbine or per MW/year), the group of beneficiaries (e.g., municipalities or citizens), and the compensation amount itself. Also, while certain Member States have legally enshrined such schemes, obligating wind park developers to compensate affected municipalities and citizens, others have not.

Thereby, financial participation and compensation schemes do have a significant impact on local acceptance (Knauf, 2022; Vuichard et al., 2019). Especially in light of the increasing push to expand wind energy – such as the EU’s requirement that Member States consider renewable energy projects as being in the overriding public interest, possibly outruling interests of birds and bats protection, or its requirement that Member States designate Renewable Acceleration Areas – the introduction of compensatory and participative measures, involving citizens, seem appropriate. That this is a general belief can also be seen in the increasing introduction of such laws. Alone in 2023/24, in Germany, six federal states have legally enshrined such a scheme or presented a draft regulation.

Despite the positive signal these schemes offer, there is still room for improvement. For instance, only few of these schemes oblige wind park operators to offer municipalities or citizens to become a shareholder in the project. Thereby, such an approach would not only be in line with the Dutch target to achieve 50% shared ownership in large energy projects by 2030, but in general, include citizens in the energy transition and share profits in a more equitable way. That such an approach is called for, has become especially evident during the gas price explosion of 2022–23 which led the EU to introduce a law requiring energy companies to share excess profits with the general public.

Also – irrespective of whether a municipality acquires “wind energy money” through project shares or by receiving a fixed amount of payments – the question of what happens next is rarely addressed in the regulations or the guidelines. Who decides how the wind energy money is being spent? One pioneering effort is a guideline presented by Denmark; here, it lays out in great detail how municipalities should organise the distribution of wind energy money, In addition, the guideline lays out that municipalities themselves are excluded from applying for the fund, making sure that it is the interests of the citizens and local companies, who are met.

5.2. An easy to use model for the estimation of job creation of individual wind farms and the need for open data.

We developed and provide an open-source python package with two alternative estimation models for the job creation potential of individual wind-farms. This can be used stand-alone and will be also integrated in the WIMBY interactive map. The model relies on data collected from scientific and grey literature. It only requires minimum parameters to run and deliver estimations divided by type of job (direct, indirect and induced) and stage in the lifetime of the wind farm (development, construction, manufacturing, operation and maintenance and decommissioning). Finally, we have added the underlying data set on job creation data to the github repository with the expectation that other interested researchers and stakeholders can contribute to it. The WIMBY job creation model is the first fully open effort to compile these data but the model results could be considerably more detailed if more data were available.

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ANNEX

Annex A: Setback distances to residential areas in ten “WIMBY countries”

Country	Min.	Max.	legally binding	additional information
Belgium				
- Flanders	250 m	250 m	yes	and considering noise, shadow flicker and safety
- Wallonia	400 m	400 m	yes	in practice 500 + ½ tip height
Denmark	476 m	1,140 m	yes	general rule 4 x tip height
Germany				
- Baden-Württemberg	700 m	700 m	yes	-
- Bavaria	10 x tip height	10 x tip height	yes	-
- Brandenburg	1,000 m	1,000 m	yes	-
- Bremen	250 m*	620 m	yes	*to villages and splinter settlements
- Hamburg	300 m*	500 m	yes	*to splinter settlements
- Hessen	1,000 m	1,000 m	no	-
- Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	800 m*	1,000 m	yes	*to splinter settlements
- Lower Saxony	2 x tip height	2 x tip height	yes	-
- Rhineland-Palatinate	500 m*	900 m	yes	*to splinter settlements
- Saarland	-	-	yes	communes may introduce setback distances
- Saxony	1,000 m	1,000 m	yes	-
- Schleswig-Holstein	400 m*	800 m	yes	*to splinter settlements
- Thuringia	1,000 m	600 m	yes	*to splinter settlements
Italy	200 m*	6 x tip height	no	*to villages
Netherlands	400 m*	600 m*	yes	*will likely be altered to 2x tip height in mid-2025
Austria				
- Burgenland	1,200 m	1,200 m	yes	-
- Lower Austria	1,200 m	1,200 m	yes	min. concerns buildings in green land
- Carinthia	1,500 m	1,500 m	yes	-
- Styria	7,00 m	1,000 m	yes	min. concerns buildings in green land
- Upper Austria	750 m	1,200 m	yes	-
Portugal	n/a	n/a	n/a	in practice defined by noise limits, hence 400 – 800 m
Switzerland	500 m	500 m	no	-
Norway	800 m	800 m	no	-

United Kingdom	n/a	n/a	n/a	in practice: 500 – 1,000 m
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Annex B: Setback distances to selected types of infrastructure in ten “WIMBY countries”

Country	Motorways	Transmission lines	Railway lines	Airports & radars	Military zones
Belgium					
- Wallonia	blade length + 10 m	1.5 + rotor diameter	200 m or (in any case) tip height + 5 m (opinion needed)	no information	no information
Denmark	1 x tip height	tip height + 15 m	tip height		5,000 m
Germany	below 40 m impossible; up to 100 m, permit needed	certain federal states introduced distances ranging between 80 m – 3 x rotor diameter	certain federal states have introduced distances ranging between 50 – 500 m	7 km to VOR	7 km to VOR
Italy	tip height + 150 m	N/A; defined by TSO	N/A; reasonably tip height + 150 m	case-dependent; typically, no problem if > 6 km	case-dependent; typically, no problem if > 6 km (concerning military airports)
Netherlands	½ rotor diameter	hub height + ½ rotor diameter (= in sum, similar to tip height)	½ rotor diameter + 7.85 m (from heart to nearest rail track)	case by case approval within 15 km radius of Schiphol	for defence radars, approval needed within a 75 km radius
Austria	1.2 x tip height (= risk assessment formula)	1.2 x tip height (= risk assessment formula)	1.2 x tip height (= risk assessment formula)	Austro Control GmbH (federal aviation agency) currently revising safety zones	1.2 x tip height (= risk assessment formula)
Portugal	50 m	turbine height	no regulation	no information	no information
Switzerland	no regulation	rotor diameter x 0.5 + 60 m	no regulation	no regulation	no information
Norway	(rotor diameter + tip height) x 1.5	(rotor diameter + tip height) x 1.5	(rotor diameter + tip height) x 1.5	case-dependent; typically, no problem if more than 6 km	10 km (radars) 25 – 50 km (airports) 10 – 24 km (shooting and training area)
United Kingdom	tip height + 50 m or tip height x 1.5	tip height + 10%	no information	15,000 km	no information

ANNEX C: Financial participation schemes in ten “WIMBY countries”

Country	description	legally binding
Belgium		
- Wallonia	wind park developers must allocate 24.99% of capital to citizen and 24.99% to municipal participation	yes
- Flanders	no specific regulation or guideline	-
Denmark		
	Bonus Scheme provides approximately up to EUR 38/MW for nearby households; Green Fund compensates municipalities with approximately EUR 42,000/MW onshore and EUR 56,000/MW offshore; guideline on how municipalities should distribute money available	yes
Germany		
- Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania	municipalities and citizens within a radius of 5 km must hold at least 20% of the operating company, either by: 1) operators sell 10% of company shares to the municipality and 10% to the citizens; maximum purchase price EUR 500; 2) operator offers a more favourable local electricity tariff; 3) transfer to municipality; net amount of electricity remunerated is offset against the forecast profit on 10% company shares; savings bond for citizens -> individual participation agreements always possible	yes
- Brandenburg	operators pay EUR 10,000/wind turbine to municipalities within a radius of 3 km (currently under revision)	yes
- Lower Saxony	0.2 cent/kWh for electricity fed into the grid to municipalities within a radius of 2.5 km; additional participation agreements must be offered to citizens and/or communes within a radius of 2.5 km	yes
- North Rhine-Westphalia	operators must enter a participation agreement with municipalities within a radius of 2.5 km	yes
- Saarland	operators must enter a participation agreement with municipalities within a radius of 2.5 km	yes
- Saxony	0.2 cent/kWh for electricity fed into the grid to municipalities within a radius of 2.5 km	yes
- Thuringia	0.2 cent/kWh for electricity fed into the grid to municipalities within a radius of 2.5 km	yes
- Bavaria	operators must enter a participation agreement with municipalities within a radius of 2.5 km; residents of the municipalities must profit from the agreement as well	yes
- Saxony-Anhalt	EUR 6/kWh for municipalities within a radius of 2.5 km	draft
Italy		
	no specific regulation or guideline	-
Netherlands		
	voluntary contributions (€0.40–0.50/MWh); Climate Agreement promotes 50% local ownership for large-scale projects.	no
Austria		
- Burgenland	Wind energy operators must pay EUR 3,000 / MW, split equally between hosting municipality and federal state	yes

Portugal	2.5% of revenues allocated to municipalities for renewable energy projects that profit from a feed-in-tariff; new projects pay €1,500/MVA, plus €13,500/MVA from the EU Environmental Fund.	yes
Switzerland	no specific regulation or guideline	-
Norway	resource rent tax of 25%; revenues allocated to host municipalities.	yes
United Kingdom		
- England	guidance on financial participation schemes exists	no
- Wales	guideline emphasises that new energy projects should include some level of local ownership	no
- Scotland	recommended community rate of approximately EUR 6,000	no
- Northern Ireland	no specific regulation or guideline	-

